

THE IMPORTANCE OF STRENGTH TRAINING IN INCREASING PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

Sh.M. Narziev¹, R.X. Mudarisova²

Professor of the Department of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Renaissance Education
University¹

Associate Professor of the Department of Natural Sciences, Uzbekistan State University of
World Languages²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17467628>

Abstract. *The article examines ways to reduce sports injuries, the significance of strength training in sports, and the physiological adaptations related to improved physical performance as a result of strength exercises. It also highlights the reduction of injuries through different types of sports.*

Keywords: *sport, physical education, strength exercises, maximum repetition, warm-up.*

Introduction.

It is no secret that significant reforms have been implemented in the development of physical education and sports in Uzbekistan. To ensure the harmonious development of the younger generation, modern sports complexes meeting state standard requirements have been built and are operating effectively. Physical education and sports must become an integral part of the overall culture of the country's citizens. At the same time, it is also true that the number of injuries caused by incorrect movements in sports has increased, which often results in an athlete's premature end to their sports career. Therefore, to reduce the dynamics of injuries and preserve athletes' health, it is necessary to implement legal, socio-economic, organizational-technical, sanitary-hygienic, medical-preventive, and rehabilitation measures in practice [1].

When addressing the issue of sports injuries, it is essential not to overlook any factor, as even a minor cause can lead to serious consequences. It should be noted that serious injuries, even if they do not require surgical intervention, can deprive an athlete of the opportunity to train fully for a long time (3–6 months) and prevent participation in competitions. The athlete's working capacity, the functional activity of their bodily systems during competitions, and the effectiveness of the training program largely depend on a properly designed warm-up. A warm-up is conducted before the main physical activity to fully prepare the body for the planned work and immediately after it to help the body efficiently transition from a state of high functional activity to rest [2]. Athletes must also be psychologically prepared for training and competition to reduce the risk of injuries. Research has shown a positive relationship between stressful life situations—especially those involving high levels of negative stress—and injuries. In understanding the stress-injury relationship, Nideffer (1983) emphasizes that muscle tension increases in response to stress. Increased tension in both antagonist and agonist muscle groups leads to decreased flexibility and loss of movement coordination. Elevated muscle tension also slows reaction time, reducing the athlete's ability to respond effectively [2.3].

Materials and methods

Strength training has been proven to be effective in improving athletic performance and is now a frequent component of many sports programs. Athletes of all kinds perform strength

exercises. Team sport athletes, however, usually lack specific physical performance characteristics, as the majority of their training time is devoted to the technical aspects of the game [3]. For example, football requires a wide range of abilities such as kicking, passing, trapping, goalkeeping, tackling, falling, jumping, running, sprinting, starting, stopping, and changing direction. Today, various types of training methods are used in sports to increase strength and power, which, in turn, enhance collective performance indicators like running and jumping. Additionally, strength and power exercises improve aerobic endurance indicators.

Modern sports training and conditioning not only lead to high levels of athletes' functional capabilities but also increase the risk of injuries [4]. Sports injuries have distinctive characteristics: in athletics—joint and ligament injuries, muscle and tissue damage; in equestrian and skiing sports—bruises, concussions, bone fractures; in boxing—concussions, bruises, cuts; in wrestling—shoulder and clavicle injuries, joint, muscle, and ligament damage, bruises, and body shocks are the most common [2,4].

An increase in blood temperature and the faster relaxation and contraction of muscles under the influence of warm-up exercises enhance intermuscular and intramuscular coordination, improve oxygen utilization within hemoglobin and myoglobin, accelerate metabolic processes, and reduce vascular resistance. All these factors contribute to improving motor performance efficiency, slowing the onset of fatigue, and accelerating recovery processes. An increase in muscle temperature promotes higher tissue metabolism. Blood flow intensifies, increasing oxygen and enzyme delivery, which naturally boosts metabolic rate. It has been established that a 10°C rise in temperature can increase chemical activity and metabolic intensity by 2–3 times. The viscosity of connective tissues and warmed muscles decreases, while their elasticity increases. As a result, productivity rises, all motor qualities and overall working capacity improve, and recovery reactions accelerate [5].

Results and Discussion.

The improvement of physical performance as a result of strength exercises and the associated physiological adaptations depends on the intensity and number of repetitions performed. It is evident that training aimed at developing optimal strength, power, hypertrophy, or muscular endurance must be carried out within different intensity “zones” to achieve the best results. During training to gain maximum strength, the intensity zone is quite narrow—ranging from 85% to 100% of one-repetition maximum (1RM). In contrast, the hypertrophy intensity zone covers a wider range, approximately from 50% to 100% of 1RM. When discussing the intensity range for power training, relatively lighter loads are used—about 0–60% of 1RM for lower-body exercises and 30–60% of 1RM for upper-body exercises—performed at a high contraction speed.

As mentioned earlier, training with loads ranging from 85% to 100% of 1RM is considered the most effective for increasing maximum strength [6]. Power can also be improved using loads corresponding to 70–80% of 1RM, although this range may be less effective than heavier loads (e.g., 85% of 1RM) for developing maximum strength in advanced power athletes.

For untrained individuals, the required intensity to increase maximum strength appears to be much lower—around 60% of 1RM. It has been suggested that intensities corresponding to 45–50% (or even less) of 1RM may increase muscle strength in previously untrained individuals. A decrease in power output leads to fatigue in the body, and fatigue may also occur if the training process is not properly organized.

- 1. Too intensive start of ineffective training - 27%,**
- 2. Excessive weight of individual training - 10%,**
- 3. Sharp increase of segments working with high intensity - 8%,**
- 4. Conducting unplanned training - 6%.**

Figure 1. Obvious mistakes that cause fatigue in the body.

Overall, research shows that strength and power training can help prevent injuries; however, poor implementation of such programs creates difficulties in successfully achieving this goal, especially in team sports [6,7]. It is impossible to completely eliminate injuries, but it is possible to reduce their occurrence. Consider this: if an athlete trains without a proper warm-up, the likelihood of injury increases by up to 85%. In such cases, muscle, bone, and musculoskeletal injuries are almost inevitable, and these can lead to serious consequences — even permanent withdrawal from sports [5,6,7]. The point is that the cardiovascular system does not adapt instantly to intense physical loads. Performing high-intensity exercises without a preliminary warm-up can cause myocardial ischemia even in healthy, well-trained athletes. For example, running on a treadmill at maximal intensity for just 10 seconds without warming up can cause pathological changes in the ECG in 68% of cases. However, when the athlete jogs lightly for two minutes beforehand, no ECG abnormalities are observed [7,8,9].

It is also appropriate to examine the physiological processes occurring in the human body. The digestion and absorption of carbohydrates occur in the small intestine. In the liver, they are converted into glucose, which in turn transforms into glycogen. Glycogen can then be stored in the muscles and liver or used by various organs and tissues as an energy source to sustain activity [10,11]. In a healthy, physically fit man weighing about 75 kg, approximately 500–550 g of carbohydrates are stored in the form of muscle glycogen (about 80%), liver glycogen (about 16–17%), and blood glucose (3–4%). This corresponds to an energy reserve of about 2000–2200 kcal.

It is clear that restoring the body's energy reserves significantly affects a person's ability to move efficiently. Below, we will discuss other important factors. Athletes and coaches must take into account temperature, humidity, and the need to adapt after traveling to extreme climates or high altitudes during training. Excessive heat and humidity, as well as cold and altitude, can negatively affect performance in many sports competitions. To prevent fatigue caused by dehydration and insufficient fluid replacement, athletes should drink additional water, juices, and other fluids. Athletes must learn to drink before they feel thirsty—by the time thirst appears, they may have already lost about 1% of their body weight. With 2% dehydration, an athlete's

performance may decrease by 10–15%. Ensuring an adequate intake of water, juices, or sports drinks helps maintain energy levels, concentration, and focus.

1. Muscle glycogen-4%. 2. Liver glycogen-16%, 3. Blood glucose-80%.

Figure 2. Energy reserves in the body of a man with sufficient physical training.

An athlete's health and safety must always come first during training or competition. If hazardous weather conditions arise, training sessions should be shortened, and training or competition schedules should be adjusted to ensure the safest possible environment for all participants. If the body is fully warmed up, the warm-up effect becomes optimal, providing not only better coordination but also physiological readiness for subsequent activity, ensuring that all systems function effectively.

Conclusion

1. Every aspect of an athlete's preparation depends on their level of perfection. Preventing premature injuries, fatigue, and illness following strength training is a key priority.

2. Safety rules during training sessions aim to minimize injuries, and warm-up exercises are mandatory for all participants.

3. Proper implementation of the process of restoring athletes' energy reserves is essential for maintaining performance.

4. Many issues should be considered when developing training programs for both team and individual sports, taking into account each athlete's performance indicators.

5. Incorporating strength training into team sports helps prevent premature muscle injuries.

REFERENCES

1. Sulaymonovich S. S., Murtozayevich N. S. Studying and accounting sports injuries //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – Т. 10. – №. 7. – С. 759-763
2. Мандриков, В. Б. Организация охраны труда и профилактика травматизма на занятиях по физической культуре : Учебно-методическа-2020.-21-25 с.
3. Платонов В.Н. Система подготовки спортсменов в олимпийском спорте. Общая теория и ее практические приложения [Текст] / В. Н. Платонов. - М. : Советский спорт, 2005.
4. AKZAMOVNA, Z. R., XABIBULLAYEVNA, S. B., KAMARDINOVNA, N. D., & TOXTABAYEVICH, B. Q. (2019). THE STUDY OF THE POLYMORPHIC GENE AGTR1

- 1166 A> C AND A MARKER OF NEPHRINE WITH DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 1 DIABETES IN THE UZBEK POPULATION. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* (09752366), 11(3).
5. Линдзей Д. и др. Принципы и методы реабилитации // Спортивная медицина. - К.: Олимпийская литература, 2003. –298-314 с.
 6. Нажмутдинова, Д. К., Рахимбердиева, З. А., & Максудова, Д. Р. (2017). Relationship of autoimmune thyroids with violations of reproductive function in women of childbearing age. *Евразийский Союз Ученых*, (2 (35)), 31-34.
 7. Нигг Б.М. Срезмерные нагрузки и механизмы спортивных травм // Спортивные травмы. Основные принципы предупреждения и лечения. - К.: Олимпийская литература, 2002. – 98-108 с.
 8. Махаматусуло‘G‘Li L. S., Murtozayevich N. S. JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORT TASHKILOTLARIDA MEHNAT MUHOFAZASINI BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI SAMARADORLIGINING MATEMATIK MODELI //Sanoatda raqamli texnologiyalar/Цифровые технологии в промышленности. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 4-1. – С. 151-156.
 9. Narziyev S. M. SPORTDA MEHNAT MUHOFAZASINI TA’MINLASHNING SANITAR-GIGIYENIK CHORA-TADBIRLARI //Sanoatda raqamli texnologiyalar. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 03.
 10. Shovkiddin N. et al. Provision Of Labor Protection And Analysis Of Injuries Of Active Participants //Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government. – 2021. – Т. 27. – №. 2. – С. 1902-1909.
 11. Murtozayevich N. S. SPORTDA MEHNAT MUHOFAZASINI TA’MINLASHNING SANITAR-GIGIYENIK CHORA-TADBIRLARI //Sanoatda raqamli texnologiyalar/Цифровые технологии в промышленности. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 197-202.
 12. Artikov Z. S. BELBOG ‘LI KURASHCHILARDA MUVOFIQLIK VA SPORT MAHORATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH //Scientific progress. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 594-597.
 13. Burxonjonovich I. I. et al. SPORT KURASHCHILARINI O ‘QUV-MASHG ‘ULOT JARAYONIDA UMUMIY JISMONIY TAYYORGARLIGI //Proceedings of Scientific Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2022. – Т. 1. – С. 2.